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TILNING NUTQQA KO'CHIRILISHI VA SINTAKTIK DERIVATSIYA HODISASI TALQINI

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Kalit so'zlar:

paramatn, o'rgatuvchi
matnlar, ma'lumotli matnlar,
fleksiyonsiz affiks, prefiks,
nol derivatsiya

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqola bilan matn va uning

hosilasi haqida tegishli ma'lumotlarni topish mumkin bo'lgan
mumkin bo'lgan misollar va nazariyalar, jumladan matn
haqidagi ma'lumotlar, hosila va nol hosila haqidagi ilmiy
omillar.

INTERPRETATION OF THE PHENOMENON OF LANGUAGE TRANSFER AND SYNTACTIC DERIVATION

Key words: paratext,
instructive texts, informative
texts, noninflectional affix,
prefixation, zero derivation

Abstract: With this scientific article one can find
relevant information about text and its derivation with
possible examples and theories which include itself
information about text, scientific factors about derivation and
zero derivation. It is believed that this research work can be
useful for every student who are conducting work relating to
this theme.

ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ФЕНОМЕНА ЯЗЫКОВОЙ ПЕРЕДАЧИ И СИНТАКСИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕРИВАЦИИ

Ключевые слова:
паратекст, инструктивные
тексты, информативные
тексты, нефлективный
аффикс, префиксация,
нулевая деривация

Аннотация: В этой научной статье можно найти
соответствующую информацию о тексте и его
происхождении с возможными примерами и теориями,
которые включают в себя информацию о тексте,
научные факторы о происхождении и нулевом
происхождении. Считается, что данная
исследовательская работа может быть полезна каждому
студенту, который ведет работу, связанную с данной
темой.

Within the field of [literary criticism](#), "text" also refers to the original information content of a particular piece of writing; that is, the "text" of a work is that primal symbolic arrangement of letters as originally composed, apart from later alterations, deterioration, commentary, translations, [paratext](#), etc. Therefore, when literary criticism is concerned with the determination of a "text", it is concerned with the distinguishing of the original information content from whatever has been added to or subtracted from that content as it appears in a given textual document (that is, a physical representation of text).

Since the [history of writing](#) predates the concept of the "text", most texts were not written with this concept in mind. Most written works fall within a narrow range of the types described by [text theory](#). The concept of "text" becomes relevant if and when a "coherent written message is completed and needs to be referred to independently of the circumstances in which it was created." [3.Б.49].

[Text linguistics](#) refers to a form of [discourse analysis](#)—a method of studying written or spoken language—that is concerned with the description and analysis of extended texts (those beyond the level of the single [sentence](#)). A text can be any example of written or spoken language, from something as complex as a book or legal document to something as simple as the body of an email or the words on the back of a cereal box.

In the humanities, different fields of study concern themselves with different forms of texts. Literary theorists, for example, focus primarily on literary texts—novels, essays, stories, and poems. Legal scholars focus on legal texts such as laws, contracts, decrees, and regulations. Cultural theorists work with a wide variety of texts, including those that may not typically be the subject of studies, such as advertisements, signage, instruction manuals, and other ephemera.

What is text and its importance in the speech

There are several definitions of the meaning of text. One of them is cited in Merriam Webster text is: **1) A (1)** the original words and form of a written or printed work

(2) an edited or emended copy of an original work

B. a work containing such text

2) **A.** the main body of printed or written matter on a page

B. the principal part of a book exclusive of front and back matter

C. the printed score of a musical composition

3) **A (1)** a verse or passage of Scripture chosen especially for the subject of a sermon or for authoritative support (as for a doctrine)

(2) a passage from an authoritative source providing an introduction or basis (as for a speech)

B a source of information or authority [2.B.57]

Another source shows that in [literary theory](#), a **text** is any object that can be "read", whether this object is a work of literature, a street sign, an arrangement of buildings on a city block, or styles of clothing. It is a coherent set of signs that transmits some kind of informative [message](#). This set of signs is considered in terms of the informative message's *content*, rather than in terms of its physical form or the medium in which it is represented.

Traditionally, a *text* is understood to be a piece of written or spoken material in its primary form (as opposed to a paraphrase or summary). A text is any stretch of language that can be understood in context. It may be as simple as 1-2 words (such as a stop sign) or as complex as a novel. Any sequence of sentences that belong together can be considered a text.

Text refers to content rather than form; for example, if you were talking about the text of "Don Quixote," you would be referring to the words in the book, not the physical book itself. Information related to a text, and often printed alongside it—such as an author's name, the publisher, the date of publication, etc.—is known as *paratext*.

The idea of what constitutes a text has evolved over time. In recent years, the dynamics of technology—especially social media—have expanded the notion of the text to include symbols such as emoticons and emojis. A sociologist studying

teenage communication, for example, might refer to texts that combine traditional language and graphic symbols.[4.B.78]

So, from my point of view, for most students, much of their time will be spent interacting with texts of all types, shapes, sizes, and delivery methods. Sound interesting? It is. So, it's important to understand what constitutes a text.

The previous page on “How to Navigate this Text” used the word “text” to mean “textbook,” referring to this digital text. If you glance at almost any page of this textbook, you'll see different elements of text: words, images, videos. Taken together OR taken separately, all of these things constitute text. A text is anything that you see, interpret, and assign meaning to.

You might have thought that texts were limited to written materials, such as books, magazines, newspapers, web pages, or blogs. Those items are indeed texts—but so are movies, paintings, television shows, songs, political cartoons, videos, advertisements, maps, works of art, and even rooms full of people. If you can look at something, explore it, find meaning in it, and draw information and conclusions from it, you're looking at a text.

So, knowing that, although this digital textbook deals primarily with written text – how to read it and how to write about it at a college level – the concepts and competencies you learn can be applied to any type of text. You'll learn to interact with text, think about it, and express ideas about it.

Conforming all above-mentioned facts, we can conclude to this section with the following scientific words. The word “text” comes from the Latin *texere*, “to weave.” Deriving from the Latin, most definitions place “text” as a linguistic structure woven out of words or signs. To call something a “text” implies that the words, phrases, lines or sentences of which it consists have not been arranged this way by chance, but have been produced by a person and with certain kinds of intentions. Therefore, a text contains meaning which is open to interpretation. In other words, A text is **a passage of words that conveys a set of meanings to the person who is reading it**. It's a body of written work, in various forms and

structures, that can be words, phrases and sentences that piece together a passage of written work.

Moreover, there are many types of the text which should be mentioned. A text can come in any form and be any kind of writing. Letters, adverts, user-guides, emails, postcards, notes and magazine articles are all different types of text. When reading something, it helps to know what type of text it is. It also helps to know why it has been written. For example:

- An advert is written to persuade you to buy something.
- A user-guide is instructive and is written to tell you how to use something (such as a video recorder or washing-machine).
- A formal (business) letter might be written to inform you about school dates.
- A personal letter might be written by a friend, describing a holiday.

Persuasive texts A persuasive text tries to encourage you to do something.

It may: • Use capital letters, exclamation marks, questions and repeated words to catch your attention.

- Use adjectives to make something sound attractive.
- Give only one side of an argument.
- Take the form of an advert; but it may also be a letter from a friend trying to persuade you to go to a class. For example, the following text is written to persuade the reader to take a holiday: Enjoy an Enchanting Holiday in the Maldives Scattered across the Indian Ocean lie islands with the finest white sand beaches and clearest crystal blue waters. These are the MALDIVES! Over 1,000 coral islands. Temperatures here are always in the 80s. What can our holiday offer you? Luxurious accommodation aboard the fabulous Orient Explorer. Water sports for the entire duration of your holiday. Drinks and entertainment included at no extra charge. Chauffeur-driven limousine to and from the airport. Combine this with another seven-night holiday in our opulent apartments at the Kelai Country Club. Prices start from just £899 per person. Have a go at spotting all the

persuading words that are used in the text. Understanding different types of text

Rt/E3.2 © BBC 2011 It's important to understand the difference between what is a fact and what is the writer's opinion. Try and work out what is fact and what is opinion in the text above.

Instructive texts. An instructive text tells you how to do something. It will often use commands and pictures. It will be direct, without extra words, like adjectives. For example: Cut the bread into small squares. Arrange in layers and sprinkle with sugar and raisins.

Informative texts. An informative text should give facts, information or news in a clear, step-by-step way. For example: Your course will start with an initial assessment in week 1, followed by a guided tour of the building.

Descriptive texts A descriptive text tells you what something is like. The writer is trying to help you imagine or 'see' a person, place or thing. Describing words, such as adjectives and adverbs are used, as well as descriptions of the five senses: look, sound, smell, touch, taste. For example: He was a big man with short curly hair, brown teeth and a flat nose. A scar crossed his right cheek from ear to chin.

Letters Texts such as letters often look the same but can have different purposes. For example:

- A personal letter from a friend can be set out in whatever way the writer wishes and will often describe a person, place or thing.
- A circular letter is sent to many people and, like an advert, will often try to persuade the reader to buy something. [5.B.102]

Here is given other examples for text from both English and Uzbek literature.

It is a truth universally acknowledged, that a single man in possession of a good fortune, must be in want of a wife. However little known the feelings or views of such a man may be on his first entering a neighbourhood, this truth is so well fixed in the minds of the surrounding families, that he is considered the rightful property of some one or other of their daughters. "My dear Mr. Bennet," said his lady to him one day, "have you heard that Netherfield Park is let at last?" Mr. Bennet replied that he had not. "But it is," returned she; "for Mrs. Long has

just been here, and she told me all about it." Mr. Bennet made no answer. "Do you not want to know who has taken it?" cried his wife impatiently. "You want to tell me, and I have no objection to hearing it." This was invitation enough. "Why, my dear, you must know, Mrs. Long says that Netherfield is taken by a young man of large fortune from the north of England; that he came down on Monday in a chaise and four to see the place, and was so much delighted with it, that he agreed with Mr. Morris immediately; that he is to take possession before Michaelmas, and some of his servants are to be in the house by the end of next week." [6. B.36]

1264-inchi hijriy, dalv oyining o'n yettinchisi, qishki kunlarning biri, quyosh botqan, tevarakdan shom azoni eshitiladir... Darbozasi sharqi-janubiyga qaratib qurilgan bu dongdor saroyni Toshkand, Samarqand va Buxoro savdogarlari egallaganlar, saroydagi bir-ikki hujrani istisno qilish bilan boshqalari musofirlar ila to'la. Saroy ahli kunduzgi ish kuchlaridan bo'shab hujralariga qaytqanlar, ko'b hujralar kechlik osh pishirish ila mashg'ul, shuning uchun kunduzgiga qarag'anda saroy jonliq: kishilarning shaqillashib so'zlashishlari, xoxolab kulishishlari saroyni ko'kka ko'targudek. Saroyning to'rida boshqalarg'a qarag'anda ko'rkamrak bir hujra, anovi hujralarga kiygiz to'shalgani holda bu hujrada qip-qizil gilam, uttalarda bo'z ko'rpalar ko'rilgan bo'lsa, munda ipak va adras ko'rpalar, narigilarda qora charog' sasig'anda, bu hujrada sham' yona-dir, o'zga hujralarda yengil tabi'atlik, serchaqchaq kishi-lar bo'lg'anida bu hujraning egasi boshqacha yaratilishda. Og'ir tabi'atlik, ulug' g'avdalik, ko'rkam va oq yuzlik, kelishgan, qora ko'zlik, mutanosib qora qoshliq va endigina murti sabz urgan bir yigit. Bas, bu hujra bino va jihoz yog'idan, ham ega jihatidan diqqatni o'ziga jalb etarlik edi.[7.B.1]

From seeing above-mentioned examples, it can be concluded that both languages have their own peculiarities according to lexical and morphological point of view.

Scientific factors about derivation

Initially, we have to know what is derivation. According to Meriam Webster derivation is the formation of a word from another word or base (as by the addition of a usually noninflectional [affix](#)) or the relation of a word to its base or root; something that originates from something else [2.Б.78]. Whereas Cambridge dictionary shows that the [origin](#) of something, such as a word, from which another [form](#) has [developed](#), or the new [form](#) itself [9. Б.67].

Hudson defines derivation as the creation of new words by the use of derivational affixes. Unlike inflectional affixes, which there are typically said to be eight in English (all are suffixes), and have very customary use, the use of derivational affixes is not obligatory. They tend to form words the meaning of which is somewhat narrower than that of their parts. A good illustration in English are result nouns, such as those ending in *-ment*, e.g. *government*, the result of governing.

An important aspect to look at when discussing derivational affixing is certainly heads and modifiers. According to Hudson [2.Б.57]“...some derivational affixes seem to bring about changes of part of speech...”. One understanding that can be given here is that derivational affixes are the heads of their words. However, prefixes, which are also derivational affixes, do not function as heads, and are in fact hardly ever word-class changing. It should be recalled that in a noun phrase, the head is a noun, and in a verb phrase the head is the verb – the head is the essential element of a phrase, towards which other elements are modifiers. Having said that, *retirement* would have the structure at the left, and *summarise* would have the structure at the right, below.

Here, *-ment* is clearly a sort of N, which obligatorily combines with verbs, and as the head of its phrase naturally yields a noun. If *-ise* is a verb, as head of its construction with a noun the result is a verb.

Some English examples include [2.p.44]

- a. ***geosynchronous*** (*geo* + *syn* + *chron* + *ous*) ‘in time with the orbit of the earth’ (of communications satellites which stay over one point on the surface of the earth). *Geo-* ‘earth’, *-syn-* ‘alike’, *-chron-* ‘time’, *-ous* ‘suffix forming adjectives from nouns’. Like typical derivations of new words in the technical fields, all the morphemes have Greek or Latin origins.
- b. ***Cabledom*** (*cable* + *dom*) ‘the cable television business and its sphere of influence’. The suffix *-dom* is quite rare, probably most encountered in the word kingdom.
- c. ***Energiser*** (*energ(y)* + *is* + *er*) ‘which causes to have energy’. The suffix *-ise* is added to nouns to form verbs with the meaning ‘cause to have the quality of the noun’. *-Er* is added to verbs to make noun instruments or agents, causers of the verb, as in *walker* ‘instrument to help walking’.

Hudson [2. Б.68] concludes that derivation is perhaps the most common way to express new meanings in English, especially when it comes to technical fields such as computer science, medicine, and the physical and natural sciences, where new

discoveries, new technology, and new ways of thinking are regular occurrences which necessitate a ready means of expression.

According to Beard, unlike inflectional morphology, derivational morphology or word formation is so named because it usually results in the derivation of a new word with new meaning. They argue that derivation is purely lexical, as opposed to inflection, which, on the other hand, is considered to be

relevant only to syntax. Therefore, the output of a derivation rule is inevitably a new word, to be incorporated into the lexicon. Lexemes, or lexical entries, upon which derivational rules operate, are considered to comprise three types of features: a phonological matrix, a grammatical subcategorisation frame, and a semantic interpretation, all of which mutually imply each other.

In addition to suffixation, prefixation in English offers a vast number of options for derivation of new words. According to Bauer, most prefixes in English are class- maintaining. However, the majority of prefixes can be added to bases of more than one form class. Some examples are:

- a. **arch-**, used exclusively with a noun base, added particularly to human nouns to denote an extreme or pre-eminent person, e.g. *archmonetarist*
- b. **de-**, used exclusively with a verb base, not so frequent partly due to its being in competition with *dis-* and *un-*, e.g. *decapacitate, deboost*
- c. **fore-**, added to nouns and verbs, e.g. *foretell, foreground, forelock*
- d. **in-**, added to nouns and adjectives, has a number of forms depending on the initial segment of the base, e.g. *inoperable, improbable, illegal*

Of the class-changing prefixes, it may be worth mentioning here the following ones:

- a. **a-**, forms adjectives from forms mainly ambiguous between nouns and verbs, e.g. *asleep, aglaze*
- b. **be-**, forms transitive verbs from adjectives, verbs or nouns, e.g. *becalm, befriend, bewitch*
- c. **en-**, forms transitive verbs mainly from nouns, e.g. *enslave, entomb*

As it has been said, in its broadest sense, derivation refers to any process which results in the creation of a new word. Beard argues that backformation could also be discussed here, given that some types of derivation do not fit into derivational lexical paradigms holding for many other bases, like the following:

Zero-Derivation

Zero-derivation is also known as ‘functional shift’ or ‘conversion’. This is the principle of using a word as another part of speech, without any affix or change of form at all. Nouns can thus become verbs, and vice versa. The phenomenon is becoming quite common in English. Verb-to-noun and noun-to-verb cases are common; others are seldom. All zero-derivation has recently been analysed as involving metonymic shifts. Some Hudson’s examples include:

- a. **swim**, basically a verb (as in ‘Can you swim?’), may be used as a noun, as in ‘have a swim’
- b. **fun**, essentially a noun (as in ‘Are we having fun yet?’), may be used as adjective, as in ‘That would be a fun thing to do.’
- c. **trail**, basically a noun (as in ‘a trail through the woods’), may be used as a verb in sports-talk, as in ‘The Pistons trailed until the second period.’
- d. **laugh**, basically a verb (as in ‘They seem to laugh a lot.’), may also be used as a noun, as in ‘We had such a laugh then.’
- e. **ring**, essentially a verb (as in ‘The phone’s been ringing for minute snow.’), may also be used as a noun, as in ‘I’ll give you a ring later today, ok?’

CONCLUSION and Suggestions

The preceding sections of this paper provide an outline of particular available means for production of new meanings in established forms of words in the English language. In order to present two major types of production of complex forms (derivation and compounding), it was prerequisite to provide some definitions and generalisations. In the focus of the theoretical part were word formation and related topics as viewed by different authors. Following are the conclusions that can be drawn:

Concerning the theoretical part of the paper, generally speaking, word formation is a largely explored area. Many authors agree on the basic principles that motivate and govern the process of word formation.

However, on the particular processes of word formation outlined in the paper, it can be said that there are areas that are relatively productive (such as compounding) given all the constraints the process of an established form of a word obtaining a new meaning can pose. Not only is each particular type discussed in this paper present in casual speech, rather it is employed quite frequently.

Overall, it can be concluded that there is definitely reason for studying language and its lexis, as Chomsky puts it [4.Б.87], “it is tempting to regard language, in the traditional phrase, as a ‘mirror of mind’”, simply because language with its lexis is a never-ending process, governed by principles that are universal by biological necessity. The variety of mechanisms that English offers for the production of new words, which have been presented in the paper, as well as the numerous corresponding examples, have shown what qualifies English as a language medium which is universally intelligible. English thus continues to occupy the position of the world’s first language.

I suggest that this topic should be widely taught throughout our country at every stage of our educational systems.

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